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Fracture mechanics testing of irradiated RPV steels by means of sub-sized specimens

Deliverable D2.2
Fabrication of unirradiated specimens

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¹ **Nature:** R -Document, report; **DEM** -Demonstrator, pilot, prototype; **DEC** -Websites, patent fillings, videos, etc.; **OTHER**; **ETHICS** -Ethics requirement; **ORDP** -Open Research Data Pilot; **DATA** -data sets, microdata, etc.

² **Dissemination level:** **PU** -Public; **CO** -Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)

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1 Introduction

FRACTESUS is a Euratom project concerning the utilization of miniature compact tension (mini-CT) specimens in fracture mechanical assessment of metallic materials in the nuclear power context. In particular, the brittle fracture initiation toughness is investigated with Master Curve methodology, standardized by ASTM as test method E1921 [1]. The primary objective is to successfully utilize mini-CT specimens in the evaluation of selected materials with nuclear relevance in non-irradiated and irradiated states and thus validate the methodology. Furthermore, the project aims to provide guidelines for later users.

Previous reports in FRACTESUS [2-6] have described the planning phase as well as the initial phase of stakeholder involvement in the project. This report describes the actions taken in the preparation of mini-CT specimens of unirradiated materials in terms of design, fabrication, and fatigue pre-cracking.

2 Background

At the beginning of the project, the test matrix for the project was finalized [2]. This included decisions on test materials and participating laboratories in the testing of each material, as well as guidelines on specimen design. All participants in unirradiated mini-CT testing and fabrication are listed in Table 1, along with their abbreviations. Most of the testing is done in interlaboratory exercises, listed in Table 2. Additional fracture toughness tests of unirradiated materials are listed in Table 3. The unirradiated materials were then delivered to the participants in 2021. The laboratories received pieces in different shapes and sizes, yet so that the intended number of mini-CT specimens could be fabricated. Furthermore, the participants were informed about the properties of the piece, such as the orientation of the piece in terms of original manufacturing and the location of the fusion line in the case of weldments.

Fabrication of specimens was done in accordance with ASTM E1921 standard requirements. In spring 2022, participating laboratories were sent a questionnaire on the progress. The form is included in Appendix A.1. Later the participants were possibly enquired for further clarification in an open format.

Table 1. Research organisations participating in unirradiated mini-CT testing in FRACTESUS project. It should be noted that EK-CER has changed their abbreviation from MTA-EK.

Institute	Abbreviation
Studiecentrum voor Kernenergie / Centre d'Étude de l'Énergie Nucléaire	SCK-CEN
ÚJV Řež, a.s.	NRI
Teknologian tutkimuskeskus VTT Oy	VTT
Framatome GmbH	FRA-G
Helmholtz-Zentrum Dresden-Rossendorf eV	HZDR
Karlsruher Institut für Technologie	KIT
Energiatudományi Kutatóközpont	EK-CER
Nuclear Research and Consultancy Group	NRG
Centro de Investigaciones Energéticas, Medioambientales y Tecnológicas	CIEMAT
Universidad de Cantabria	UC
Paul Scherrer Institut	PSI
The University of Birmingham	UoB
Culham Centre for Fusion Energy (United Kingdom Atomic Energy Authority)	CCFE
Central Research Institute of Electric Power Industry	CRIEPI

Table 2. Test matrix draft of unirradiated round-robin exercise. N_{test} denotes the nominal number of tests per participant. N_{mat} denotes the nominal amount of material per participant, that is "how many specimens could be fabricated from delivered material at least".

RR No.	Material	Orientation	Provider	T0	N_{test}	N_{mat}	Testing participant				
							1	2	3	4	5
1	15Kh2MFAA	L-S	HZDR	-134	16	20	SCK-CEN	CRIEPI	HZDR	VTT	EK-CER
2	A533B (JRQ)	T-L	NRI	-71	16	20	NRI	CRIEPI	PSI	CCFE	
3	73W	T-L	SCK-CEN	-64	16	20	SCK-CEN	CIEMAT	HZDR	VTT	UoB
4	SA508 Cl.3	R-C	CIEMAT	-43	16	20	SCK-CEN	CIEMAT	KIT	NRG	UoB
5	ANP-5	T-L	FRA-G	-38	16	20	SCK-CEN	FRA-G	HZDR	CCFE	UC
6	A533B LUS (JSPS)	T-L	SCK-CEN	+8	16	16	SCK-CEN	CRIEPI	UC		

Table 3. Test matrix for additional unirradiated fracture toughness tests outside the round-robin exercises.

Material	T0 [°C]	Tester	No. of tests
15H2MFA	-134	MTA-EK / BZN	16
SA 533 B1	-119	CIEMAT	16

3 Specimen design

Specimen design was initially covered already in the planning phase and reported by Arffman [2]. After fabrication, however, the essential dimensions were surveyed again in case there were changes to previous plans.

In general, the design was only required to follow the recommendations of ASTM E1921 [1]. During the assessment of the fracture mechanical test results differences between participants' designs are then considered, particularly if test results vary greatly. Table 4 summarizes the essential dimensions of the specimens from each participant. Table 5 describes the labels used for the dimensions. Some of the main details to consider are listed below:

- a. VTT and SCK-CEN utilize two different specimen designs in the project. The designs corresponding with each material are listed in Table 6. VTT designs are very similar to each other. SCK-CEN has produced duplicate series of specimens from four interlaboratory investigation materials, and possible effects of the differences can thus be distinguished.
- b. Some participants have slightly larger specimens than the majority (10mmx9.6mmx4mm). The standard evaluation considers different specimen sizes and scales the fracture toughness results accordingly. ASTM E1921 does require proportionality of the specimen in terms of width W , height H , and thickness B . Therefore, the results should be comparable, and the specimens are still well within the scope of miniaturization. In any case, the test results will be assessed accordingly.
 - i. SCK-CEN (II) and PSI have overall larger specimens. The specimens are scaled proportionally.
 - ii. EK-CER specimen has a larger height than proportional. Since their pinhole distance H^* and crack opening displacement (COD) distance Δ is similar to the others, the additional material on the top and bottom of the specimen should have a limited effect on the stress state in the crack tip, and subsequently the fracture toughness.
 - iii. KIT specimen is elongated in the front, that is, the total width of the specimen W_{tot} is larger. This should not influence the fracture toughness since the effective width W is the same as the majority.
- c. CIEMAT and PSI have larger holes for the loading pins. PSI hole is proportional to the other participants, and standard suggestion. The size is expected to not have a pronounced effect on the results, but the performance of pins of different diameters shall be considered.
- d. COD measurement location divides participants. Some have gages attached to the front face (FF) of the specimen, while others mount it on the load-line (LL). The methods are considered equal, but an additional rotation correction must be applied if COD is measured from the front face.

- e. In contrast to other participants, PSI utilizes a load-line displacement gauge in crack length determination. That is, the crack opening displacement is not measured. The method is accepted by the standard, but again, the difference shall be considered while assessing the test results.
- f. The lengths of the machined notch a_0 vary. This means that the fatigue pre-cracks are different lengths. As long the pre-crack fulfils the standard requirements, different a_0 has no impact. Considering the pre-crack length and curvature, possible effects become evident only once the specimens have been tested and the crack surfaces evaluated.

Table 4. Specimen dimensions of the specimens of each participating laboratory. "VTT I", "VTT II", "SCK-CEN I" and "SCK-CEN II" refer to the two different designs at corresponding laboratories. Dimensions of participants marked with an asterisk are retrieved from [2].

PARTICIPANT	W	W _{TOT}	H	a ₀	H*	Δ	D	B
VTT I	8	10	4.8	3.2	2.25	4.5	2	4
VTT II	8	10	4.8	3.2	2.2	4.5	2	4
CRIEPI	8	10	4.8	3	2.2	1.5	2	4
EK-CER	8	10	5	2.5	2.2	4.5	2	4
NRG	8	10	4.8	3.2	2.2	4.5	2	4
PSI	9	11.25	5.4	4.75	-	-	2.25	4.5
SCK-CEN I	8	10	4.8	2.4	2.2	4.3	2	4
SCK-CEN II	8.3	10	5	2.7	2.3	4.5	2	4.2
UC	8	10	4.8	3.2	2.2	1.5	2	4
KIT	8	11.5	4.8	4	2.2	2	2	4
FRA-G	8	10	4.8	2.7	2.2	2.5	2	4
CIEMAT	8	10	4.8	3.2	2.25	4.5	2.1	4
HZDR	8	10	4.8	3	2.2	1.5	2	4
CCFE*	8	10	4.8	3	2.2	1.5/4.5		4
NRI*	8	10	4.8	3	2.2	1.5		4
UOB*	8	10	4.8	3.2	2.75	4.5		4

Table 5. Descriptions of specimen dimensions are listed in Table 4.

LABEL	DESCRIPTION
W	Specimen width
W_{TOT}	Full width
H	Specimen height
a₀	Length of machined notch
H*	A half span of applied load points
Δ	A half span of displacement measurement points
D	Diameter of loading pinhole
B	Specimen thickness

Table 6. Materials investigated by VTT and SCK-CEN on different specimen designs, as listed in Table 4.

VTT I	VTT II	SCK-CEN I	SCK-CEN II
	15Kh2MFAA	15Kh2MFAA	
		ANP-5	ANP-5
73W		73W	73W
		A508 Cl. 3	A508 Cl. 3
		A533B LUS (JSPS)	A533B LUS (JSPS)

4 Fabrication of specimens

In terms of unirradiated materials, most participating laboratories in FRACTESUS have finished fabrication. SCK-CEN is participating in five exercises and has yet to fabricate the last series of specimens. This is expected not to affect the project.

Regarding fabrication methods, participants are utilizing EDM for machining. In general, specimen fabrication has been successful. VTT and SCK-CEN encountered some workshop errors in fabrication, but the series can still be tested. Furthermore, CIEMAT had challenges in the fabrication of the end of the machined notch. While not a miniaturization issue, smaller sizes and features may increase the chance of manufacturing mistakes. Nevertheless, workshop errors should be considered a preventable risk, but miniaturized specimens may require particular attention.

In general, issues in fatigue pre-cracking of the specimens seemed to be most prevalent. At VTT, COD measurement at the load-line during pre-cracking was unreliable. The COD clip gauge does not measure the unloading compliance of the specimen adequately at high fatigue frequencies. Lowering the frequency alleviated the issues, suggesting that the problem might be related to test frame vibrations, the bluntness of the load line notch and subsequent movements of the clip gage in the notch. Further investigations are required, but fatigue pre-cracking with COD measured from the front face provides acceptable crack fronts as of now. In an earlier FRACTESUS meeting, NRG mentioned that they had similar issues.

UC also encountered unreliability in unloading compliance measurement during fatigue pre-cracking, although they measure COD from the front face. In their case, the method seems to overestimate the

crack length. Their solution was to combine unloading compliance with optical measurements of the specimen.

Contrary to the aforementioned issues with fatigue pre-cracking, HZDR regarded the latest alleviation of pre-crack curvature requirements to be helpful. The number of invalid samples was much lower than if an older edition of ASTM E1921 had been used.

Regarding the homogeneity of the materials, KIT deemed the SA508 Cl.3 received by them to be highly inhomogeneous, also regionally. They fabricated their specimens in the region of lowest inhomogeneity. While the material block received by them was larger than the ones utilized by SCK-CEN and CIEMAT in the same interlaboratory study and allowed such regional selection, differences in test results can be expected. In another interlaboratory exercise, EK-CER had crack propagation during fatigue pre-cracking stopped locally in some specimens. They considered this to be caused by inhomogeneity, and vanadium carbide precipitates in particular, of the material.

KIT further mentioned that ice build-up on the specimen surface, pins and clevises is a problem, particularly during tensile tests that they are performing additionally. This can be an issue during fracture toughness testing and should be considered in the design of test equipment.

5 Deviations

The deliverable is late due to constrained human resources at all stages. The passing of the project coordinator caused further delays in the deliverable. The delays in the deliverable, however, are not expected to impact the project's progress, since the fabrication of specimens has been done on time and the testing of materials is well underway.

6 Conclusion

The specimen designs between participants vary. The differences are generally minor, but they should nevertheless be considered. Since the tests are mostly done in interlaboratory exercises, potential differences can be pointed out.

In general, the preparation of unirradiated specimens has largely been successful. Workshop issues encountered by some participants are something to keep in mind since the fabrication of miniature specimens requires more precision than that of larger ones.

Other than that, fatigue pre-cracking has been the cause of most challenges. The problems were mostly solved by utilization of front-face COD measurement and support of the optical assessment of crack growth. However, all pre-cracking issues might not be evident before testing has ended and fracture surfaces have been investigated.

The deliverable aims to support further work in FRACTESUS, in particular the assessment of any discrepancies in test results and formulation of general guidelines for mini-CT utilization in fracture toughness evaluation. Furthermore, experience gained in unirradiated materials fabrication will be carried forwards to the fabrication of specimens from irradiated materials.

7 References

- [1] ASTM E1921-21, *Standard Test Method for Determination of Reference Temperature, T_0 , for Ferritic Steels in the Transition Range*, ASTM International, West Conshohocken, PA, 2021.
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- [4] S. Cicero and B. Arroyo, "Data Management Plan (DMP) – 1st version," in "Fracture mechanics testing of irradiated RPV steels by means of sub-sized specimens (FRACTESUS)," D6.8, 2021.
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APPENDICES

A.1. Questionnaire template

In addition to the form below, the participants were asked to provide the essential dimensions and drawings of their specimen designs, as well as specimen cutting plans.

Your name, participating organization	
Have you received all the materials allocated to you in the test matrix?	
Have you started the fabrication of specimens from the materials?	
If not, has there been unexpected issues?	
If yes, have you finished the fabrication? Did you encounter any problems/challenges/curiosities? Did you have to make any changes to original plans?	
If you have already started fatigue pre-cracking/testing the materials, have you identified any problems/challenges/curiosities related to specimen fabrication?	
Any additional comments?	

A.2. Cutting schemes

Figure 1 Cutting scheme of 15Kh2MFAA material (block received from HZDR). 20x specimens of "9.6x10" design

Figure 2 Cutting scheme of ANP-5 material (material received from FRA-G). 20x specimens of design "9.6x10" and 18x specimens of design "10x10" (T-L orientation)

Figure 3 Cutting scheme of unirradiated 73W material (offered by SCK CEN). 19x specimens of "9.6x10" design and 19x specimens of "10x10" design

D.2.1 - Fabrication of unirradiated specimens

Figure 4 Cutting scheme of A508 Cl.3 material (received from CIEMAT). 20x specimens of “9.6x10” design and 20x specimens of “10x10” design.

Figure 5 Cutting scheme of A533B LUS (JSPS) material (offered by SCK CEN). 16x specimens of “9.6x10” design and 16x specimens of “10x10” design. Four specimens to be produced from half of broken 0.5T-CT

b. CRIEPI

Figure 6. 15Kh2MFAA

Figure 7. A533B (JRQ)

16 x Mini-C(T) specimens in T-L

Figure 8. A533B LUS (JSPS)

c. UC

	DIBUJADO: Marcos Sánchez y Borja Arroyo		FECHA 30/03/2021
	LADICIM	FRACTESUS; ANP5	
ESCALA 4:1		Cotas en mm	Nº PLANO 01

Figure 9. ANP-5

	DIBUJADO: Marcos Sánchez y Borja Arroyo		FECHA 11/10/2021	
	LADICIM	MINI CT; ACERO A533 LUS		Nº PLANO 01
ESCALA 4:1		Cotas en mm		

Figure 10. A533B LUS

d. KIT

e. PSI

- 1
 - Rohmaterial Reststücke zum Kunde zurücksenden.
 - Reststücke ohne Materialzeichnungen, mit dem Materialname **5/JRO56C1** beschriften (Wasserfesten Stift erlaubt)
 - Reststücke ohne Orientierung, mit Wasserfesten Stift T, L und S markieren!
- 2
 - Abstände zwischen den Proben kann nach Bedarf gewählt werden. Es müssen mindestens 24 Proben heraus Erodert werden.

2	25	Stk.	4603.50.002	0.18CT-Probe K 0.25mm	
1	1	Stk.	4603.50.1011	Rohmaterial JRQ 12x12x116mm	
Pos.	Menge	Einheit	Sachnummer	Benennung / Merkmale	
a			d	Gezeichnet	06.01.2022 BE46
b			e	Gepufft	
c			f	Archiviert	
Anlage Spannungsrissskorrosion				Ersetzt durch	
Baugruppe				Ersetzt fuer	
Proben				Stueckl. Nr.	
				Zusammenst.Nr.	1/1
Titel: Probenentnahmeplan JRQ 12x12x116mm				Zeichnungs-Nr.: 4603.50.1010	Blatt 1 / INVENTOR:2019

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f. HZDR

Figure 11. 15Kh2MFAA

Figure 12. A533B (JRQ)

Figure 13. 73W

Figure 14. ANP-5

g. CIEMAT

Figure 15. 73W

Figure 16. SA508 Cl.3